

Required Heating Energy in Buildings: A Comparative Analysis of Mathematical Models based on Standard HRN EN ISO 52016-1, Neural Networks, Grey Box, and Measured Data.

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ABSTRACT

University North, the only Croatian participant in the "Program energetske obnove zgrada javne namjene" from 2014 to 2020, employed the ESCO model for energy renovations. This model entails repaying the initial investment through energy savings, with guaranteed savings defined based on standardized parameters. Post-renovation, deviations in energy consumption may occur due to altered building usage patterns influenced by user behavior and external factors. Integration of the Artificial Neural Network (ANN), grey box modeling, and standard HRN EN ISO 52016-1 offered insights into energy consumption patterns and user behavior impact. Comparison of measured data with ANN, grey box model, and norm results enhanced energy efficiency strategies for building management. University North aims to optimize energy consumption, enhance occupant comfort, and promote sustainability in the public sector. The ANN, trained on parameters like temperature, humidity, VOC, and CO₂, acts as a "black-box" model predicting energy consumption without explicit physics knowledge. The grey box model, incorporating some physics principles, provides a basis for comparison. Standard "HRN EN ISO 52016-1 Energy performance of buildings - Energy needs for heating and cooling; internal temperatures and sensible and latent heat loads" is considered a "white-box" model due to its basis in physics laws and heat transfer models, offering transparency and explainability. This research aims to develop a simulation model for continuous HVAC system optimization, increasing energy efficiency and savings in buildings.

KEYWORDS

Energy Building Renovation, Standard HRN EN ISO 52016-1, User Impact on Energy Consumption, Artificial Neural Network, Grey Box Modeling

1. INTRODUCTION

The building sector in the European Union is responsible for a substantial portion of energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions, accounting for 40% of total energy use and 36% of emissions. Notably, 80% of the energy used in buildings is devoted to heating, cooling, and domestic hot water preparation. In response to the urgent threat of climate change, the European Council committed in December 2020 to reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030, compared to 1990 levels, with the aim of achieving climate neutrality by 2050 [1]. However, the EU faces significant challenges in the global energy market, which has prompted the implementation of the REPowerEU plan, designed to save energy, produce clean energy, and diversify energy supply [2]. As part of this broader effort, National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) were introduced under the Regulation on the Governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action (EU) 2018/1999, which was agreed upon as part of the Clean Energy for All Europeans package adopted in 2019. These NECPs outline how member states intend to contribute to the Energy Union's goals, particularly in improving energy efficiency and sustainability [3].

A key strategy in reducing energy consumption is the deep renovation of buildings, which focuses on comprehensive upgrades to building envelopes, energy systems, and control systems. This long-term strategy aims to renovate the national building stock by 2050, with the goal of significantly reducing energy consumption for heating, cooling, and hot water [4]. However, it has been observed that partial renovations, such as those focusing solely on the building envelope or energy systems, often yield only modest energy savings [5]. In some cases, these partial renovations may even lead to an increase in energy consumption, highlighting the need for more comprehensive renovation approaches. Reasons for that could be due to reduction of indoor air quality [6], specifically increase in the concentration of carbon dioxide and volatile organic compounds [7]. One of the significant challenges in building renovations is the performance gap—the difference between predicted and actual energy consumption post-renovation. This gap can arise from various factors, including meteorological conditions, user behavior, discrepancies between design and as-built conditions, and variations in building usage [8]. For instance, one study found that while calculated energy savings might range between 59% and 71%, the actual savings achieved were as low as 33%, due to atypical building usage patterns and changes in user behavior following renovations [9]. Moreover, changes in user behavior post-renovation can further increase this gap [10].

During the project "Program energetske obnove zgrada javne namjene" from 2014 to 2020, a deep energy renovation of the building complex (UNIN1, UNIN2, and UNIN3) at the University North in Varaždin was carried out. The energy renovation was financed using the ESCO (Energy Service Company) model, which allows the initial investment to be repaid based on the energy savings achieved after the renovation. Under this model, the energy service provider is compensated from the difference between pre-renovation and post-renovation energy costs, with no additional costs incurred by the user. After the contractual obligation ends, the user benefits from paying their actual, now reduced, energy costs. However, it has been observed that the delivered energy often differs from calculated consumption due to various factors such as user behavior, building usage, and external environmental conditions like outdoor air temperature, ventilation, and solar radiation. These variations make the University North complex an ideal live laboratory for studying energy efficiency in buildings.

Given the importance of accurately assessing energy savings from building renovations, reliable mathematical models are crucial. These models help quantify the impact of renovations and address the performance gap by considering variable factors such as external and internal

climatic conditions, building usage, and user behavior [11]. Since all these factors are hard to model and predict it is crucial to have a valid method and guidelines for baseline model [12]. Using data from Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) sensors is advised to use in correlation with energy performance contracts to minimize performance issues and manage energy performance tradeoffs of IEQ against energy performance that could lead to occupants health consequences [13].

Mathematical models for energy consumption are generally divided into white, black, and gray box models. White box models are based on detailed physical laws and heat transfer mechanisms, offering transparency but requiring significant expertise and computational resources. Black box models, in contrast, rely on statistical methods and historical data, offering high execution speed but with less interpretability [14]. Gray box models combine elements of both approaches, providing a balance between transparency and accuracy [15]. Comparative analyses have shown that while black box models may offer higher prediction accuracy, their applicability is limited due to their complexity and data requirements [16]. On the other hand, gray box models have shown promise in balancing prediction accuracy and computational efficiency, making them suitable for more complex building systems. These models could also be applied in implementing Model Predictive Control (MPC) to achieve additional energy savings and potentially decrease the return on investment for energy contractors. MPC has demonstrated potential for achieving significant energy savings and reducing peak loads, although its implementation in real-world scenarios remains limited [17].

The development and application of robust mathematical models are crucial for accurately assessing energy savings in renovated buildings. These models play a vital role in understanding and mitigating the performance gap between predicted and actual energy. However, despite advancements in model development, existing models often become overly complex, tailored to specific buildings, and difficult to apply universally, making them time-consuming and resource intensive. To address these challenges, this paper focuses on the application of the HRN EN ISO 52016-1 standard, which is complex enough to capture building dynamics and usage patterns while remaining practical for broader application. To enhance the model's accuracy and applicability, standardized coefficient values and assumptions were refined through real life testing. Two specific tests were conducted: the Pseudo Random Binary Sequence (PRBS) test, which examines changes in indoor temperature in response to random patterns of heating source operation, and a ramp-up test, where the indoor temperature is raised to a stationary value and after turning off heat source the subsequent temperature decrease is observed. These tests were performed under controlled conditions, such as when the building was unoccupied (no internal gains from occupants) and solar gains were negligible (e.g., at night or during very cloudy days), allowing for the determination of internal gains from equipment, specific heat capacity of zones, and infiltration rates.

This approach aims to balance model complexity with practical applicability, ultimately leading to more reliable predictions of energy savings post-renovation. In addition to the white box model based on HRN EN ISO 52016-1, this paper also explores the use of an RC thermal model (gray box) and an Artificial Neural Network model (black box). By comparing these three common approaches to thermal modeling, the paper provides valuable insights into their respective strengths and limitations, offering a comprehensive perspective on building energy modeling.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Measurement and building description

The University North complex, located in Varaždin, consists of three main buildings: UNIN 1, UNIN 2, and UNIN 3. UNIN 1 and UNIN 2 primarily house classrooms and laboratories, while the administrative offices of the University are situated in UNIN 3. The UNIN 1 building, located at 104th Brigade Street 3, is a four-level structure comprising a basement, ground floor, first floor, and attic. However, only the rooms on the ground floor and first floor are furnished and operational, providing a total heated usable area of 1,570 m² and a heated volume of 7,949 m³. The building is equipped with sensors and measurement devices to monitor temperature (°C), relative humidity (%), CO₂ concentration (ppm), and Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC) concentration (ppb) in each room. Each room is equipped with at least one sensor, while larger rooms are equipped with multiple sensors (Figures 1 and 2) to ensure accurate data collection across the space.

Figure 1. Ground floor UNIN1

Figure 2. First floor UNIN1

In addition to indoor environmental monitoring, meteorological data are continuously recorded. This data includes wind speed, wind direction, external relative humidity, solar radiation, and outdoor temperature, all measured by a weather station located within the University North complex. The indoor microclimatic parameters and outdoor environmental data are recorded at 15-minute intervals. The gas consumption of the building's heating system is measured and logged hourly for most of the period, during PRBS test gas consumption was measured and logged at 5-minute intervals. Gas consumption data is converted to delivered energy using a conversion factor of 9.2607 kWh/Sm³, where 1 Sm³ is the standard cubic meter of natural gas under standard conditions (pressure of 101 325 Pa and temperature of 288.15 K).

Continuous monitoring of indoor and outdoor parameters, along with the delivered natural gas quantity, was conducted from October 1, 2021, to August 1, 2024. The recorded data was processed to align with full-hour intervals. In cases where data were not recorded exactly on the

hour, values were linearly interpolated. Solar radiation data, however, represents the sum of measurements over the preceding hour. The accuracy of the measurement devices used in the study is provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Accuracy of the measurement devices

Measurement Location	Device Type	Device Description	Measurement range	Accuracy
Gas Measurement	Itron ACD G10	Diaphragm Gas Meter	0.10-16 m ³ /h	Class 1.5
Weather Station	Davis Vantage PRO2	Meteorological Station for Measuring External Temperature, Relative Humidity, Wind Speed and Direction, and Solar Radiation	Temperature: -40 to +150°C Relative Humidity: 1-100% Wind Speed: 0-809 m/s Wind Direction: 0-360° Solar Radiation: 0-1800 W/m ²	Temperature: +/- 0,3°C Relative Humidity: +/- 2% Wind Speed: 1 m/s Wind Direction: 3° Solar Radiation: 5% of full scale
		Sensor for Temperature, Relative Humidity, CO2 Concentration, and Volatile Organic Compounds	Temperature: -40 to +125°C Relative Humidity: 0-100% CO2 Concentration: 0-5000 ppm VOC Concentration: 0-60000 ppb	Temperature: +/- 0,2°C Relative Humidity: +/- 2% CO2 Concentration: - VOC Concentration: -
In room sensors	Enless AMB 600-023			

To capture the building's dynamic thermal response, a Pseudo Random Binary Sequence (PRBS) test was performed. The PRBS test introduced varying heating power inputs over time, allowing observation of the indoor temperature's response to these fluctuations. This test was crucial for accurately calibrating both the grey box and white box models, enabling them to capture the building's thermal dynamics effectively. Additionally, a temperature ramp-up test was conducted by setting the heating system to its maximum capacity to reach a stationary indoor temperature. Once the stationary temperature was achieved, the heating system was turned off, and the resulting temperature drop was recorded. This data was used to fit the zone's thermal capacity and internal gains, providing essential input for the grey and white box model's thermal parameters.

2.2. Mathematical models

This study uses three different types of models to analyze the energy usage in the building: a white box model based on thermodynamic laws, a black box model driven purely by data, and a grey box model that integrates both data-driven approaches and physical principles. Each of these models was developed using open source programming language Python.

2.2.1. *White box model – HRN EN ISO 52016-1*

White box models stand out for their transparency, providing a clear understanding of the background of the process. On the other hand, their complexity requires highly qualified personnel and a significant amount of time during development.

The calculation of the energy required for heating a building is based on the HRN EN ISO 52016-1 standard [18], which provides guidelines for calculating the necessary energy for heating buildings. The process of calculating the required heating energy involves gathering data on the building's properties, determining climatic conditions, zoning the space, identifying heat losses, and calculating the required energy for heating.

When gathering data on the building, it is necessary to consider the building's area, volume, the surface area of the exterior walls, the type and thickness of insulation, and the type of windows and doors. The climatic conditions affecting the building's heating include outdoor temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, and solar radiation, which are collected at the weather station located on the building's roof.

The energy required for heating the building is calculated using formulas that consider heat losses and climatic conditions, and the energy equation for a zone describes the heat exchange between the building and its environment. By following these steps, it is possible to accurately calculate the required energy for heating a building in accordance with the HRN EN ISO 52016-1 standard. Energy equation for zone is written in equation (1) with following equations for layer of wall in contact with zone (2), equation for inside layers of wall (3) and layer of wall with contact with outside environment (4).

$$\left[C_{int;ztc} + \sum_{eli}^{eln} (A_{eli} \cdot h_{ci,eli}) + \sum_{vei=1}^{ven} H_{ve;vei;t} + H_{tr;tb;ztc} \right] \cdot \theta_{int;a;ztc;t} - \sum_{eli=1}^{eln} (A_{eli} \cdot h_{ci,eli} \cdot \theta_{pli,eli;t})$$

$$= \frac{C_{int;ztc}}{\Delta t} \cdot \theta_{int;a;ztc;t-1} + \sum_{vei=1}^{ven} (H_{ve;vei;t} \cdot \theta_{sup;vei;t}) + H_{tr;tb;ztc} \cdot \theta_{e;a;t} + f_{int}$$

$$\cdot \Phi_{int;ztc;t} + f_{sol} \cdot \Phi_{sol;ztc;t} + f_{H/C} \cdot \Phi_{HC;ztc;t}$$
(1)

$$-(h_{pli-1;eli} \cdot \theta_{pli-1;eli;t}) + \left[\frac{\kappa_{pli;eli}}{\Delta t} + h_{ci;eli} + h_{ri;eli} \cdot \sum_{elk=1}^{eln} \left(\frac{A_{elk}}{A_{tot}} \right) + h_{pli-1;eli} \right] \cdot \theta_{pli;eli;t} - h_{ci;eli}$$

$$\cdot \theta_{int;a;ztc;t} - \sum_{elk=1}^{eln} \left(\frac{A_{elk}}{A_{tot}} \cdot h_{ri;eli} \cdot \theta_{pli;elk;t} \right)$$

$$= \frac{\kappa_{pli;eli;t-1}}{\Delta t} \cdot \theta_{pli;eli;t-1} + \frac{1}{A_{tot}}$$

$$\cdot [(1 - f_{int;c}) \cdot \Phi_{int;ztc;t} + (1 - f_{sol;c}) \cdot \Phi_{sol;ztc} + (1 - f_{H/C,c}) \cdot \Phi_{HC;ztc;t}]$$
(2)

$$-h_{pli;eli} \cdot \theta_{pli-1;eli;t} + \left[\frac{\kappa_{pli;eli}}{\Delta t} + h_{pli;eli} + h_{pli-1;eli} \right] \cdot \theta_{pli;eli;t} - h_{pli;eli} \cdot \theta_{pli+1;eli;t}$$

$$= \frac{\kappa_{pli;eli}}{\Delta t} \cdot \theta_{pli;eli;t-1}$$
(3)

$$\left(\frac{\kappa_{pli;eli}}{\Delta t} + h_{ce;eli} + h_{re;eli} + h_{pli;eli} \right) \cdot \theta_{pli;eli} - h_{pli;eli} \cdot \theta_{pli+1;eli;t}$$

$$= \frac{\kappa_{pli;eli}}{\Delta t} \cdot \theta_{pli;eli;t-1} + (h_{ce;eli} + h_{re;eli}) \cdot \theta_{e;t} + \alpha_{sol;pli;eli}$$

$$\cdot (I_{sol;dif;eli;t} + I_{sol;dir;eli;t} \cdot F_{sh;obst;eli;t}) - \Phi_{sky;eli;t}$$
(4)

Standard HRN EN ISO 52016-1 requires a lot of input data and most of them are shown in Table 2. The ones that are not mentioned in table and are in calculation procedure of the standard are values specified in standard and are not changed.

Table 2. HRN EN ISO 52016-1 input data

Description	Symbol	Value	Unit of Measurement
Number of air changes in hour	n	0.8	1/h
Zone height	H	3.5	m
Zona area	A	1 570	m ²
Specific heat capacity of air and furniture	κ_{int}	524 600	J/m ² K
Specific heat capacity of walls	κ_{m}	1 069 692	J/m ² K
Thermal transmittance of walls	U_{wall}	0.22	W/m ² K
Thermal transmittance of windows	U_{window}	1.31	W/m ² K
Thermal transmittance of roof	U_{roof}	2.51	W/m ² K
Thermal transmittance the ground-contact wall	U_{ground}	0.19	W/m ² K
Internal gains	Q_{int}	8	W/m ²

From November 17, 2022, to November 21, 2022, a natural cooling test ("Free floating temperature") of the building was conducted. This test begins by heating the building to stationary indoor air temperature conditions, which are significantly higher than the usual indoor air temperatures, using the boiler at maximum power. Once stationary conditions are achieved, the boilers are turned off, and no further thermal energy is supplied to the rooms. The indoor air temperature naturally decreases due to the lower outside temperature and air infiltration through the building envelope, until a new stationary point and indoor air temperature are reached. During the test conducted from November 17 to November 21, the stationary temperature after cooling the building was not achieved, as the heating of the spaces began when the building was put back into use. The aim of this test was to determine internal gains from equipment, such as computers, lighting, and other equipment used in the building during the test period. Another goal was to verify whether the properties of the building envelope correspond to the design values, which was examined with known infiltration determined from the drop in CO₂ concentration, measured during the test.

2.2.2. *Black box model – Acyclic Neural Network*

Machine learning is a branch of artificial intelligence. Within the domain of machine learning, neural networks are the most prominent. An artificial neural network is a data processing system designed based on the example of neurons in biological systems, specifically their interconnections. Each neuron in the network performs calculations and is interconnected by "weighted" connections that are determined during the training of the neural networks with known data. In this work, a feedforward artificial neural network is used, which, like most, is composed of an input layer, hidden layers, and an output layer, which in this case has only one output value. The number of neurons in each of the hidden layers is determined experimentally, i.e., by trial and error, with a focus on ensuring that the network is not overly complex, as this could jeopardize its applicability to input data sets different from those on which it was trained, leading to the phenomenon of "overfitting."

The input data consists of measured data from all rooms within the building and external environmental parameters, as described previously. In a later chapter, the chosen architecture of the neural network, which consists of an input layer, four hidden layers with the following number of neurons: 250, 200, 100, 50 and an output layer composed of one neuron representing the desired value, i.e., the delivered energy for heating the building. Figure 3 shows the scheme of the feedforward neural network where the first layer is the input layer, followed by four hidden layers,

and finally, the output layer. The activation functions used in the hidden layers are Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU), while the output layer uses a linear activation function.

Figure 3. Visualization of Acyclic Neural Network

The training and testing of the neural network were done using measured data normalized to the full hour, with gas consumption transformed into delivered energy. Meteorological data and indoor thermal comfort parameters were measured during the periods from October 1, 2022 – June 1, 2023. The data used to train and later test the neural network were randomly divided in a 70:30 ratio, with 70% of the available data used for training the network and the remaining 30% for testing. The measured data, as input variables in the input layer, were supplemented with information about the hour of the day and the day of the week for each measured value.

2.2.3. Grey box model – 2R2C thermal model

Grey box modeling represents a hybrid approach that combines the strengths of both white-box (physics-based) and black-box (data-driven) models. In the context of building energy simulations, grey box models aim to capture the essential physical processes while also allowing for data-driven tuning to improve accuracy and robustness. One commonly used grey box model shown in Figure 4 is the 2-resistor, 2-capacitor (2R2C) model, which simplifies the thermal dynamics of a building into two primary elements: resistance and capacitance. The resistances (R) represent the thermal resistance, or the difficulty with which heat flows between different parts of the building or between the building and its surroundings. The capacitances (C) represent the thermal mass, or the ability of building materials to store heat.

Figure 4. 2R2C Thermal model

The 2R2C model divides a building into two main thermal nodes: the indoor air temperature and the envelope temperature (associated with the building's structure, such as walls and roof). The resistances and capacitances in this model are used to describe how heat transfers between these nodes and between the building and the external environment.

The core of the 2R2C model consists of a set of differential equations that govern the heat exchange processes. These equations consider factors such as internal heating (e.g., from HVAC systems), solar gains (e.g., through windows), and heat losses to the environment. The two main equations (5) and (6) describe the change in indoor air temperature and the envelope temperature over time, incorporating the effects of thermal resistance and capacitance.

$$T_i^{(t+1)} = T_i^{(t)} + \frac{dt}{C_i} \left(\frac{1}{R_i} (T_e - T_i) + \Phi_h + A_i \Phi_s \right)^{(t)} \quad (5)$$

$$T_e^{(t+1)} = T_e^{(t)} + \frac{dt}{C_e} \left(\frac{1}{R_i} (T_i - T_e) + \frac{1}{R_o} (T_o - T_e) + A_e \Phi_s \right) \quad (6)$$

For example, the change in indoor temperature (T_i) is influenced by the heat flow from the envelope to the interior, the heating power applied inside the building, and solar radiation. Similarly, the change in envelope temperature (T_e) depends on the heat exchange between the interior and exterior, as well as between the envelope and the external environment.

These equations can be represented in a state-space form, which is common in control theory and allows for systematic analysis and simulation. The state vector in this model includes the indoor and envelope temperatures, and the input vector typically includes external conditions like outdoor temperature, solar radiation, and heating power.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results are organized into three sections corresponding to the three models used in this study: the white box model, the grey box model, and the black box model. These sections present a detailed comparison of the models' performance, focusing on indoor temperature predictions and heating energy consumption.

3.1. White box model – Indoor temperature and energy used for heating

The white box model, developed according to the HRN EN ISO 52016-1 standard, was initially validated through a natural cooling test (Figure 4). The results demonstrated a high degree of accuracy in matching the calculated and measured indoor temperatures, achieved by fine-tuning the internal heat gains from equipment and adjusting the specific heat capacity of the zone. This test is a crucial method for validating the quality of the building envelope's construction and design. The results provide essential data on the building's thermal properties, including specific heat capacities of the zone as well as internal heat gains from equipment, which were determined to be 8 W/m².

Figure 4. Natural cooling test

Two primary calculations were performed using the HRN EN ISO 52016-1 model. The first calculation involved predicting indoor temperature using the measured heating energy as an input, while the second calculation focused on determining the heating energy required to maintain a known indoor temperature. It is important to note that the calculation of energy needs differs from the measured energy due to factors such as distribution losses, heat emitters inefficiencies, and energy source losses. The model's predictions were compared against measured data, starting from a period before February 11 to account for initial conditions across the wall layers. The results, shown in Figure 5, indicate that the model closely follows the demand for heating energy, with delays that probably occur due to missing distribution and heat emitters models.

Figure 5. Calculated and measured energy needed for heating – White box

The calculated energy consumption for the period was 4 656 kWh, while the measured consumption was 4 839 kWh, representing a 4% difference. This discrepancy aligns well with expected energy losses due to distribution and heat transfer, validating the model's accuracy. The temperature predictions on Figure 6, averaged across all zones, also closely matched the measured temperatures, with minor deviations observed around March 19 when heating was off, and presumably the model did not capture solar gain spikes.

Figure 6. Calculated and measured indoor air temperature – White box

3.2. Grey box model – Indoor temperature

The grey box model, utilizing the 2R2C thermal model, demonstrated an even closer match to the measured indoor temperatures. This improvement is attributed to the data-driven nature of the model, which allows for more accurate parameter tuning. The coefficients used in the model are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. 2R2C model coefficients

Coefficient	R_i	R_o	C_i	C_e	A_i	A_e
Value	0.075	1.64	4.11e7	1.64e6	0.041	-0.11

Figure 7. Calculated and measured indoor air temperature – Grey box

The grey box model's ability to incorporate both physical principles and real-world data makes it a powerful tool for predicting indoor temperatures. The results in Figure 6 indicate that the model captures the building's thermal dynamics more effectively than the white box model. This is particularly evident around March 19th, where the grey box model accurately predicts a temperature spike despite the absence of heating. These results provide a robust basis for further analysis of energy use in the building.

3.3. Black box model – Predicted energy consumption for heating

The black box model, powered by a feedforward artificial neural network (ANN), was tested using data collected prior to the PRBS test. The ANN was trained on data from the 2022/2023 heating season, covering the period from October 1, 2022, to June 1, 2023. The trained model was subsequently used to predict heating energy consumption for a two-day period between February 12 and February 14, with the results presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Predicted and measured energy needed for heating – Black box

Measured energy consumption for this period was 763 kWh, while the predicted consumption was 818 kWh, a difference of 7%. This level of accuracy shows that the trained network was not “overfitted” but still hour by hour results shows inaccurate results in some cases indicating model could benefit from general reduction in input data or even adding additional data that is crucial for energy consumption, e.g. solar irradiance or concentration of VOC where high VOC values could make occupants increase ventilation. Although the black box model showed highly accurate results, it is important to note that it lacks the physical interpretability of the white and grey box models. This limitation makes the black box model less reassuring for use in scenarios where a clear understanding of the underlying processes is essential. Possible advantages of black box model are detection in IEQ changes, system and sensors faults since all measured data is required.

3.4. Discussion

The comparison of these three models highlights their respective strengths and weaknesses. The white box model, grounded in physical laws, offers a transparent and interpretable approach but requires extensive input data and complex calculations. The grey box model strikes a balance between accuracy and computational efficiency, providing reliable predictions with a simpler set of equations. The black box model, while highly accurate, lacks interpretability, which may limit its applicability in some contexts.

Future work will focus on refining each of these models. For the white box model, this includes incorporating distribution energy losses and losses in heat generation. The grey box model will be further developed to calculate heating energy requirements directly, enhancing its utility. The black box model will be expanded to include additional variables, such as VOC concentration, to improve its accuracy, though care will be taken to avoid overfitting. Another potential avenue for the black box model is exploring alternative machine learning approaches, such as Random Forest models, which may offer similar accuracy with better interpretability.

4. CONCLUSION

The development and validation of the white, grey, and black box models for predicting building energy consumption have demonstrated the unique strengths and challenges associated with each approach. The white box model, based on the HRN EN ISO 52016-1 standard, provided a transparent and physically grounded framework for estimating heating energy needs. Its complexity and the extensive data requirements make it a rigorous tool, but also one that requires careful calibration and understanding of the underlying physical processes.

The grey box model, utilizing the 2R2C thermal approach, offered a balanced combination of physical modelling and data-driven techniques. This hybrid model successfully captured the thermal dynamics of the building with a simplified set of equations, making it a practical tool for real-world applications where both accuracy and computational efficiency are important. The black box model, powered by an artificial neural network, excelled in accuracy, particularly in predicting short-term energy consumption. However, its lack of interpretability and reliance on large datasets and high computational power make it less suitable for applications where understanding the physical processes is crucial.

The successful application of the PRBS test was a critical step in validating the white and grey box models under dynamic conditions. This test generated vital data that refined the models,

enhancing their accuracy in simulating real-world scenarios. Additionally, the second test, where the heating system was set to maximum until a stationary indoor temperature was reached, followed by a period of monitoring the temperature decrease after the heating was turned off, provided key insights into the building's thermal properties, particularly the specific heat capacity of the zone. Further testing, planned during the summer vacation, will focus on modeling solar irradiance on vertical surfaces. These tests will offer valuable insights, especially for refining the white box model.

Moving forward, each model will be further refined to enhance its utility and accuracy, ensuring they are prepared for comparison with data from the upcoming 2024/2025 heating season. For the white box model, future work will concentrate on incorporating energy losses associated with distribution and heat generation, enabling a more accurate comparison with delivered energy. The grey box model will be extended to directly calculate heating energy requirements, leveraging its simplicity and accuracy. The black box model will be refined by incorporating additional variables, such as VOC concentrations, and exploring alternative machine learning methods like Random Forest models, which may offer improved interpretability without sacrificing accuracy.

In conclusion, while each model has its specific applications and limitations, together they offer a comprehensive toolkit for calculating building energy consumption and predicting indoor temperature conditions. Continued development and testing will ensure these models remain valuable resources for building management, energy efficiency improvements, and reducing the return on investment period for energy contractor agreements.

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NOMENCLATURE

$C_{int;ztc}$	- Internal thermal capacity of the zone [J/K]
Δt	- Time step [s]
$\theta_{int;a;ztc;t}$	- Indoor air temperature [°C]
$\theta_{int;a;ztc;t-1}$	- Indoor air temperature in the previous time interval (t-Δt) [s]
A_{eli}	- Surface area of element eli [m ²]
$h_{ci;eli}$	- Internal convective heat transfer coefficient of element eli [W/m ² K]
$\theta_{pIn;eli;t}$	- Indoor surface temperature of element eli [°C]
$H_{ve;vei;t}$	- Total ventilation heat exchange coefficient for element eli [W/K]
$\theta_{sup;vei;t}$	- Supply air temperature [°C]
$\theta_{e;a;t}$	- Outdoor air temperature [°C]
$H_{tr;tb;ztc}$	- Total heat transfer coefficient for thermal bridges [W/K]
f_{int}	- Convective fraction of internal gains [-]
f_{sol}	- Convective fraction of solar radiation [-]
$f_{H/C}$	- Convective fraction of heating/cooling system [-]
$\Phi_{int;ztc;t}$	- Total internal heat gains [W]
$\Phi_{sol;ztc;t}$	- Direct solar radiation into the zone [W]
$\Phi_{HC;ztc;t}$	- Heating or cooling load in the zone [W]
A_{elk}	- Surface area of element elk in zone ztc [m ²]

A_{tot}	- Surface area of all elements $elk=1\dots eln$ [m ²]
$\theta_{pli;eli;t}$	- Temperature of node pli [°C]
$\theta_{pli-1;eli;t}$	- Temperature of node pli-1 [°C]
$\theta_{int;a;ztc;t}$	- Indoor air temperature in the zone [°C]
$h_{pli-1;eli}$	- Conductivity between nodes pli and pli-1 [W/mK]
$\kappa_{pli;eli}$	- Surface heat capacity of node pli [J/m ² K]
$h_{ci;eli}$	- Heat transfer coefficient of the internal surface [W/m ² K]
$h_{ri;eli}$	- Radiative heat transfer coefficient of the internal surface [W/m ² K]
$\theta_{pli;eli;t-1}$	- Temperature of node pli in the previous time interval (t-Δt)
$\theta_{pli+1;eli;t-1}$	- Temperature in node pli+1 [°C]
$h_{pli+1;eli}$	- Conductivity between nodes pli+1 and pli [W/mK]
$\theta_{e;t}$	- Outdoor temperature [°C]
$h_{ce;eli}$	- Heat transfer coefficient of the external surface [W/m ² K]
$h_{re;eli}$	- Radiative heat transfer coefficient of the external surface [W/m ² K]
$\alpha_{sol;pli;eli}$	- Solar energy absorption coefficient on the external surface [-]
$I_{sol;dif;eli;t}$	- Diffuse solar radiation [W/m ²]
$I_{sol;dir;eli;t}$	- Direct solar radiation [W/m ²]
$F_{sh;obst;eli;t}$	- Shading factor of element eli due to external obstructions [-]
$\Phi_{sky;eli;t}$	- Thermal radiation towards the sky [W]
T_e	- Envelope temperature [°C]
T_i	- Indoor temperature [°C]
T_o	- Outdoor temperature [°C]
R_i	- Thermal resistance between indoor air temperature and the envelope [K/W]
R_o	- Thermal resistance between outdoor air temperature and the envelope [K/W]
Φ_h	- Heating power [W]
Φ_s	- Global horizontal solar irradiance [W/m ²]
A_e	- Envelope solar gain coefficient [m ²]
A_i	- Indoor solar gain coefficient [m ²]
C_e	- Heat capacitance of envelope [J/K]
C_i	- Heat capacitance of interior [J/K]

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